

Photochemical behavior of colloidal lignin particles under controlled UV exposure: Balancing self-stabilization and degradation

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ABSTRACT

Colloidal Lignin Particles (CLPs), with their polyphenolic structure, are promising sustainable alternatives to chemical UV filters. This study investigates the photochemical behavior of CLPs under ultraviolet irradiation synthesized from five different technical raw lignins (Alkali, Organosolv, two Enzymatic Hydrolyzed and Softwood Kraft Lignin) via solvent-shift procedure. The suspensions were irradiated using a self-developed UV-pen set-up and a commercially available UV chamber, enabling controlled UV exposure over time. Variations in the physicochemical properties of irradiated colloidal lignin particles were characterized by Multi-Angle Dynamic Light Scattering (MADLS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) coupled with chemometrics, UV-Vis spectroscopy, and High-Performance Size Exclusion Chromatography (HP-SEC). CLPs exhibited comparable responses after 14 days of UV exposure, with alterations in particle chemistry, particularly in the formation of new functional groups and molecular rearrangement. Moreover, the photochemical stability of CLPs was found to be highly dependent on both their concentration and the nature of the dispersion medium (aqueous, hexane-based, and solid-state). At higher concentrations (1.8 mg/mL), CLPs demonstrated effective self-stabilization, while lower concentrations led to rapid degradation, resulting in the disappearance of particles and the formation of low-molecular-weight fragments. Additionally, Minimal photochemical changes were observed in non-aqueous or solid-state environments due to restricted molecular mobility. These findings provide valuable insights into the degradation pathways and stability across different environmental contexts, which can contribute to understanding the potential environmental impact of CLPs in aquatic ecosystems.

1. Introduction

The ongoing research advancements pursue the search for biobased and sustainable alternatives to traditional materials, focusing on circularity and the inclusion of industrial by-products as feedstock. Additionally, the global shift towards biobased materials is supported by policy frameworks aimed at reducing carbon footprints and enhancing resource efficiency.

Lignin, the second most abundant biopolymer on Earth [1], represents a significant untapped resource in this context. Its intrinsic multi-

functionality and industrial availability as a residual side-stream from pulping industries and biorefineries, has led to increased interest in this bio-sourced compound for manufacturing new biobased materials and formulations with applications in different fields such as polymers, coatings, electronics, biomedicine, cosmetics, and personal care.

Despite its abundance, technical or raw lignins are not readily usable in the industry due to their heterogeneous and complex structures as lignin polymer can present a multiplicity of structures depending on its origin and extraction process and therefore, an additional conversion process is usually required (i.e. chemical modification, refining, etc.).

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Recently, the conversion of irregular-sized lignin powder to CLPs has emerged as a promising solution for the creation of a homogeneous lignin material with controlled physicochemical properties. Lignin micro- and nanoparticles have been produced by different approaches and a combination of chemical and physical methods [2]. The anti-solvent precipitation is one of the most studied methods since it enables the production of particles of different sizes and morphologies by varying process parameters such as lignin type, initial concentration, solvent system, precipitation rate, etc [3]

The great interest in lignin particles lies in their biocompatibility, biodegradability, and low toxicity [4]. Moreover, their unique bioactive and functional properties (i.e. antioxidant, ultraviolet absorption and antimicrobial capacities) [5–7] offer a promising solution for replacing traditional and environmentally damaging additives like commercial organic UV filters (i.e. 3–4-methylbenzylidene-camphor, benzophenone-3) and antioxidants (BHA, BHT, parabens) which are commonly used in synthetic polymers, coatings, cosmetics, and personal care products. Recently, traditional UV filters, such as oxybenzone and octinoxate, which are commonly used in sunscreens and cosmetics, have been banned or restricted in certain regions for their ecological impact. Numerous studies evidenced not only their widespread presence in aquatic ecosystems and toxic effects on marine life, particularly coral reefs [8], but also their potential to bioaccumulate in living organisms [9] and their link to adverse health effects, ranging from skin irritation to hormonal disruption [8,10]. In this context, lignin's inherent photoprotective properties have inspired its use as a UV absorber across various fields, and particularly as a natural alternative to partially replace organic UV filters in sunscreen formulations [11].

Chemically, lignin is a complex amorphous polymer composed of three phenylpropane units: syringyl (S), guaiacyl (G), and *p*-hydroxyphenyl (H). These monomers are linked via carbon-carbon (C–C) and ether (C–O–C) linkages, forming a highly branched and cross-linked structure. Moreover, lignin has plenty of chromophores and auxochromes, including conjugated double bonds within the aromatic rings and side chains of its phenylpropanoid units, carbonyl groups, aliphatic and phenolic hydroxyl and methoxy groups. These functional groups, together with the molecular weight properties of lignin, are intrinsic factors that play a crucial role in its photochemical behavior and the inherent UV-shielding properties of polymeric lignin [12]. Additionally, the morphology of lignin particles is also a factor influencing their properties. A higher UV-shielding capacity of colloidal lignin particles compared to other shapes was reported based on their greater surface area-to-volume ratio [13,14]. Further, the ordered molecular structure of those lignin particles enhances the π -conjugation system and therefore also improves its photothermal conversion capability [15,16]. The incorporation of nanoparticulated lignin as a UV absorber for polymer films has been widely investigated, resulting in enhanced UV-shielding capacity while acting as a nano-reinforcement providing improved mechanical and thermal properties [17,18]. Moreover, lignin particles have been evaluated as a bioactive ingredient for sunscreen formulations, providing a variety of beneficial properties such as UV protection capacity, antioxidant activity, and emulsification ability by offering a greener alternative to synthetic compounds in sunscreen and skincare products [13,19–22].

Despite their potential as environmentally friendly alternatives to traditional UV filters, the interaction mechanisms of colloidal lignin particles remain poorly understood. The understanding of the behavior and stability of lignin particles in different environments (i.e. under UV irradiation) is vital to advance the development of lignin-based nanomaterials and their high-performance application in various commercial products. Their unique nanoscale properties, such as enhanced dispersibility in water and greater surface area, may lead to superior interaction with light and water, significantly influencing their photostability under UV exposure.

Under UV irradiation, lignin's primary chromophoric structures degrade, resulting in the formation of secondary chromophores. These

chemical transformations resulting from the UV light absorption have been extensively studied, particularly in wood chemistry [23] and the pulp and paper industry, where the wood discoloration [24,25] and the yellowing of papers produced from mechanical pulps [26], attributed to the photoreactivity of lignin, have been a great challenge for years.

Due to the high complexity of lignin, many researchers investigated model compounds to clarify the main structural elements that contribute to lignin's photochemical behavior. The photodegradation mechanism involves the formation of phenoxy radicals, which are further oxidized to quinones and other chromophores [27]. Direct photolysis of phenolic hydroxyl groups or the hydrogen atom abstraction from phenolic hydroxyl group by an excited carbonyl group are two proposed mechanisms for the formation of phenoxy radicals [23]. The excitation of α -carbonyl groups may also contribute to the cleavage of the β -O-4 ether linkages in lignin resulting in a radical formation [28]. Additionally, it was observed that methoxyl groups, present in syringyl and guaiacyl units, increase electron delocalization, thereby inducing the photodegradation process [29].

Given the growing interest in colloidal lignin particles (CLPs) as a natural alternative to synthetic UV filters in cosmetics and related applications, and the lack of prior studies specifically addressing their behavior under UV irradiation, this research aims to fill a critical knowledge gap by systematically evaluating the photochemical response of CLPs. To this end, five lignins from different botanical and industrial sources were processed into particles using a solvent-shifting process. These particles were exposed to UV irradiation in both solid-state and dispersed forms (in water and hexane). A UV pen system was carefully configured to ensure consistent and reproducible irradiation. The goal was to examine how the chemical nature of the original lignins and the irradiation conditions affect the UV absorbance, molecular characteristics, and structural integrity of particles. The study employs various analytical techniques, including gel-permeation chromatography, UV spectroscopy, particle size analysis, and FTIR coupled with chemometrics, to assess the physicochemical changes induced by UV exposure. This study provides, for the first time, insights into the behavior of CLPs under UV exposure. These findings are particularly relevant for applications in cosmetics, packaging, and coatings, where sustainable UV protection is increasingly in demand.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

The CLP suspensions were produced using the following materials: organosolv lignin (OS) derived from beech wood (Fraunhofer CBP, Leuna, Germany), softwood kraft lignin (SKL) supplied by Valmet company, alkali lignin (AL) from grass (Protobind 1000, PIT Innovations, Rüschiikon, Switzerland), and two variants of enzymatic hydrolysis lignins sourced from beech (EH1) and birch wood (EH2). Additional components included ethanol (EtOH) (96 wt%, AustraAlco GmbH, Spillern, Austria) and ultra-pure water (18 M Ω -cm). For irradiation trials ultra-pure water (18 M Ω -cm) and n-Hexane (≥ 95 %, Carl Roth GmbH+Co KG, Karlsruhe, Germany) was used. For analytical performances ethanol (EtOH) (100 wt%, Chem-Lab NV, Zedelgem, Belgium) and Sodium Hydroxide was used.

2.2. Preparation of colloidal lignin particles (CLPs)

CLPs were prepared from various lignin raw materials, including alkali lignin, enzymatically hydrolyzed lignin, organosolv lignin, and softwood kraft lignin. Despite the different initial extraction methods, all raw materials underwent a standardized procedure to produce CLP suspensions. Briefly, the lignin was dissolved in an aqueous ethanol solution (60 wt% EtOH for AL, OS, EH and SKL and 80 wt% EtOH for EH2), followed by a precipitation process to form colloidal particles as described in previous works by Beisl et al. and Adymczyk et al. [30,31]

The resultant CLP suspensions were then purified and concentrated using diafiltration in a membrane process to remove residual solvents and impurities [32]. This procedure was carried out by Lignovations GmbH. All CLP suspensions were diluted with ultra-pure water to the same concentration of 3.6 wt%.

2.3. UV irradiation

CLP suspensions were diluted with ultra-pure water to the same 1.8 mg/mL concentration. Additionally, the EH2 CLP system was selected to test the effect of environmental conditions and the solvent matrix's impact on the CLPs' photostability. EH2 CLPs were freeze-dried, redispersed (1.8 mg/mL) in hexane and subjected to a long-term irradiation protocol of 14 days. To evaluate the effects of UV exposure on CLPs in solid form, EH2 CLP suspension was air-dried at ambient temperature in 5 cm Petri dishes, ensuring a uniform distribution of particles over the surface of the substrate.

Under controlled conditions, CLP suspensions were irradiated using a UV pen (PenRay® Lamp UVP 90-0004-01, mercury lamp). The lamp emitted radiation with key maxima at 184.9, 253.6, 312.5, 365, 404.7, and 435.8 nm, with a relative intensity of 4.4 mW/cm² at a 1.9 cm distance. The CLP suspensions (1.8 mg/mL) were placed in a tall beaker containing 200 g and continuously stirred to ensure homogeneous irradiation. The beaker was cooled to approximately 10 °C to prevent overheating and unwanted evaporation, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The samples were exposed to UV radiation for 14 days, with 5 mL aliquots collected daily (from day 0 to day 14) for subsequent analysis. Investigations of the influence of CLP concentration on the kinetics of the photodegradation process were conducted by diluting the EH2 CLP suspension to 0.72 mg/mL (D1) and 0.36 mg/mL (D2).

The air-dried lignin particles were placed inside a UV chamber (BS-03 UV/VIS Irradiation Chamber, Opsytec) and subjected to continuous irradiation under controlled conditions. The chamber provided UVA (5.1–5.8 mW/cm²) and UVB (1.0–1.20 mW/cm²) radiation. At the same time the temperature was maintained at approximately 20 °C through an air-cooling system to prevent excessive heating and degradation due to high temperature. The samples were irradiated for a total duration of 25 days. The samples were collected at specific time intervals (after 3, 7, 14, 21, and 25 days) to assess potential chemical and structural changes induced by prolonged UV exposure.

2.4. Characterization of CLP suspensions

The morphology and primary particle size of the CLPs were analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Quanta 200 FEG-SEM, FEI, Hillsboro, OR, USA) at an acceleration voltage of 5 kV. Prior to measurement, the samples were sputter-coated twice with 4 nm of Au/Pd

(60:40 wt%). The primary particle size was manually assessed using ImageJ software, with the reported values representing the averages and standard errors from 150 measurements.

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to analyze both the raw lignins and CLPs before and after UV irradiation. The samples were scanned in triplicate in the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ range at 4 cm⁻¹ of spectral resolution, and accumulated an average of 64 scans with an Alpha II compact FT-IR spectrophotometer (Bruker Optik GmbH, Ettlingen, Germany) equipped with a diamond crystal with attenuated total reflectance (ATR) unit. For CLPs, samples were freeze-dried before analysis. The obtained IR database was filtered and processed by applying extended multiplicative scatter correction (EMSC), standard normal variate (SNV) and mean centering. PLS-Toolbox analytical software tool (Eigenvector research incorporated) was used for signal processing and data analysis.

The UV absorbance spectra of the CLPs were measured using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV-1800, Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) within the wavelength range of 190–400 nm. To avoid scattering interference caused by variations in particle size, the CLPs were dissolved in a 60 wt% aqueous ethanol solution prior to analysis. The dilution with ethanol was adjusted to 0.1 mg/mL to ensure that the CLP concentration in the ethanolic solution was consistent across all samples. In order to evaluate the structural changes during UV irradiation qualitatively, the absorption spectra data were area normalized as described in Eq. (1). This approach does not account for CLPs irradiated at decreased concentrations which underwent substantial degradation, leading to a reduced absorption ability after prolonged irradiation.

$$I_{i,norm} = \frac{I_i}{\sum_{240}^{400} I_i} \cdot f \quad (1)$$

$I_{i,norm}$ area normalized absorption at wavelength i
 I_i absorption at wavelength i
 f factor

The molecular weight distribution was analyzed with high performance size exclusion chromatography (HPSEC) using 10 mM NaOH as an eluent. Three columns, in series, at 40 °C (PW5000, PW4000, PW3000; TOSOH Bioscience, Darmstadt, Germany) were used with an Agilent 1200 HPLC system (flow rate: 1 mL/min, DAD detection at 280 nm, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The CLP suspensions were diluted with ultra-pure water, and through the addition of NaOH the same pH as present in the eluent was reached. The columns were calibrated using polystyrene sulfonate reference standards (PSS GmbH, Mainz, Germany) with molar masses of 78,400 Da, 33,500 Da, 15,800 Da, 6430 Da, 1670 Da, 891 Da, and 208 Da at their peak maxima.

Fig. 1. Schematic Illustration of a) CLP suspension preparation for irradiation trials and b) UV-Pen set up (Created in <https://BioRender.com>).

The size of the aggregated CLPs in the aqueous suspension was measured using a Zetasizer Ultra (Malvern Panalytical GmbH, Kassel, Germany) via Multi-Angle Dynamic Light Scattering, MADLS. The refractive index of the CLPs was set to 1.53, and the imaginary refractive index was set to 0.1. The reported values represent the averages and standard errors from three independent measurements.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physicochemical characterization of CLPs

Five different types of technical lignins (Table S1 in supplementary information) were utilized to produce colloidal lignin particles through a solvent-shifting precipitation method. The solubility of each lignin in aqueous ethanol varied significantly due to their distinct chemical properties. During the precipitation process, the lignin particles underwent self-assembly, which, according to Xiang et al. [15], enhanced the π -conjugation by transforming disordered lignin aggregates into organized colloidal particles, following the supramolecular self-assembly mechanism.

In the solvent-antisolvent process, the lower molecular weight lignin fractions and impurities remained in the aqueous phase. Consequently, diafiltration was employed to remove these impurities and to achieve highly stable colloidal suspension. The diafiltration was followed by concentration, both steps conducted through membrane filtration as described in previous work done by Miltner et al [32]. This procedure was designed to standardize the particle size and surface properties. The produced CLPs exhibited similar surface characteristics and, therefore, comparable behavior and properties, regardless of the lignin source.

The primary particle size and morphology of the CLPs was analyzed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). Pictures in Fig. S1 in SI 3 show spherical shapes of all tested CLPs and sizes of 28, 40, 47, 81 and 47 nm for AL, OS, EH, EH2 and SKL., respectively. The differences in particle size between samples suggest that the synthesis conditions including solvent concentration and lignin source, influence particle formation. Additionally, the particle size distribution of colloidal lignin particles (CLPs) was analyzed using Multi-Angle Dynamic Light Scattering (MADLS). The intensity-weighted size distributions revealed distinct aggregation behaviors across different CLP samples (Fig. S2). AL exhibited three peaks, suggesting a broad size distribution with multiple aggregation states. OS and SKL showed a bimodal distribution, where OS displayed a main peak around 400 nm indicating that this sample primarily consisted of larger aggregates. Interestingly, OS also exhibited a secondary peak at 220 nm, suggesting the presence of smaller aggregates co-existing with larger aggregates. This bimodal distribution indicates a complex aggregation behavior and may reflect a balance between particle nucleation and growth or the inherent polydispersity of the organosolv lignin feedstock. In contrast, SKL primarily consisted of smaller aggregates centered around 180 nm, with a minor peak at 400 nm indicating some degree of aggregation. EH and EH2 showed a single dominant peak, highlighting a more uniform particle distribution with reduced aggregation. Table 1 presents the average size distribution of

CLPs and z-potential values ranging from -30 mV to -40 mV indicating stable colloidal dispersions [33]. The discrepancies between MADLS and SEM results arise due to the fundamental differences in their measurement principles. MADLS analyzes particle size within an aqueous matrix, where it detects agglomerates or aggregated colloidal particles, leading to larger measured diameters. In contrast, SEM provides direct imaging of dried samples, enabling the measurement of primary particle diameters without the influence of aggregation. The phenomenon of aggregation dependency on primary particle size is described in earlier works [22]. The aggregation occurs due to the higher surface energy of smaller particles [34]. However, the result of this study also indicates that the formation of agglomerates is influenced by the origin of the bulk lignin, as particles derived from EH lignin exhibit a lower tendency to agglomerate compared to CLPs from AL, OS and SKL.

The molecular weight properties of produced CLPs were analyzed by HPSEC solubilizing the particles in a sodium hydroxide solution (aqueous). CLPs presented a narrower and more defined molecular weight distribution compared to the broader profile of the raw technical lignin, indicating a clear fractionation effect during particle formation (Fig. S3a). EH lignin was used as a representative example, and similar effect was observed for all CLP samples (Fig. S3b), confirming that the particles production process selectively influences the molecular weight characteristics of the resulting particles [35]. The molecular weight distribution of the CLPs is strongly influenced by the solubility of the raw lignins in the selected solvent. Consequently, direct comparisons with literature data are not meaningful, as differences in solubilization conditions significantly affect the molecular weight.

All CLPs showed a similar UV absorption profile (Fig. S4) with (i) a strong absorption below 280 nm, which corresponds to the $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ electronic transitions of aromatic rings present in lignin, (ii) a shoulder around 280 nm associated with non-conjugated phenolic groups, and (iii) a gradual decrease in absorption at longer wavelengths. The differences in absorption intensity and peak positions suggest variations in their chemical structures due to different extraction methods and origin [36,37]. AL and SKL CLPs have their maximum at 280 and 281 nm respectively, this slight red shift might be due to the increased hydroxyl group content present in these CLPs [38] and an increased conjugation particularly for SKL CLPs. The maxima of OS at 275 nm and, EH and EH2 at 278 nm are characteristically for hardwood lignins [39,40] and less conjugated structures. Moreover, Organosolv and enzymatically hydrolyzed lignins exhibit structural similarities to native lignin [16]. As can be seen, AL and SKL CLPs reveal the same absorbance values between 300 and 360 nm which are also related to the high presence of hydroxyl groups that are known for broadening the absorption spectrum [40] and further the electron transition from conjugated carbonyls.

Fig. 2 shows vibrations of the fingerprint region in the range of 1700–800 cm^{-1} of CLP samples (AL, EH, EH2, OS, and SKL) and Table S2 summarizes the band assignment corresponding to the identification of 11 peaks identified. The FT-IR spectra revealed distinct patterns that correspond to the structural components of lignin. The aromatic ring vibrations of the phenylpropane skeleton, characteristic of lignin are observed at 1596, 1510, and 1421 cm^{-1} (#1, #2, #3) in all samples. These peaks are a hallmark of lignin's aromatic structure and are consistently present across the sample set [41–43]. At 1458 cm^{-1} (#4), the peak shows variability: it appears broader in AL and SKL, whereas it is sharper in EH, EH2, and OS, suggesting structural differences associated with C–H deformation vibrations in methyl ($-\text{CH}_3$) and methylene ($-\text{CH}_2$) groups within the lignin structure [44,45]. The weak signal around 1369 cm^{-1} (#5) originating from acetate C–H in methyl groups appeared as clear broad band in SKL while absent in other lignin samples. The band at 1326 cm^{-1} (#6), present only in EH, EH2, and OS, and very weak in AL, is attributed to syringyl ring breathing with C–O stretching [45]. This observation aligns with the theoretical monomeric composition of lignin derived from these specific feedstocks. The 1269 cm^{-1} (#7) peak is less pronounced, while 1215 cm^{-1} (#8), indicative of C–O and C–H vibrations in the guaiacyl ring, is shifted in AL lignin,

Table 1

Morphological characteristics: Size of agglomerated particles measured by 1: MADLS and primary particle size evaluated via 2: SEM picture analyses.

	Z-average (nm) ¹	Polydispersity index ¹	Zeta potential (mV)	Average primary particle size (nm) ²	Standard deviation primary particle size (nm) ²
AL	351.1	0.26	-35.9	28	8.2
OS	313.5	0.20	-34.5	40	11.2
EH	74.9	0.14	-35.9	47	15.3
EH2	160.2	0.12	-42.3	81	21.0
SKL	182.9	0.26	-43.4	47	12.7

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectra of untreated CLP suspensions.

possibly due to unique phenolic group interactions. At 1200 cm^{-1} , a band related to C—O stretching in hydroxyphenyl units is noted, potentially explaining the shift in the AL lignin peak at 1215 cm^{-1} . The 1125 cm^{-1} (#9) peak, linked to syringyl lignin, is evident across all samples and is indicative of aromatic C—H in-plane deformation and syringyl ring breathing with C—O stretching. This band is particularly strong in hardwood lignins, which have a higher S/G ratio, as syringyl units contain more methoxy ($-\text{OCH}_3$) groups than guaiacyl units [46]. However, the 1115 cm^{-1} (#10) peak is strongly present in EH, EH2, and OS, highlighting aromatic C—H deformation. This band is associated with in-plane aromatic C—H bending vibrations, prominent in lignins with a higher syringyl unit proportion, particularly from hardwood sources.

3.2. UV irradiation experiments

The CLP suspensions with a concentration of 1.8 mg/mL were irradiated using the UV-pen set-up over 14 days. Samples were taken regularly from day 0 (d0) until day 14 (d14) and analyzed by SEM, MADLS, HPSEC, UV/Vis spectroscopy and FT-IR.

Multi-Angle Dynamic Light Scattering (MADLS) measurements were performed to evaluate how UV-induced molecular changes affect the particle size of CLPs. Fig. 3 presents the intensity-weighted particle size distributions of the irradiated samples. For AL CLPs, a slight decrease in agglomerate size was observed over the irradiation period. OS CLPs initially showed a broad size distribution, which gradually evolved into a bimodal profile, indicating partial deagglomeration. In the case of EH CLPs, a subtle deagglomeration trend was also detected, primarily affecting the larger aggregates. A comparable pattern was observed for both EH2 CLPs and SKL, suggesting that UV irradiation induces mild restructuring or partial disaggregation across all samples. Furthermore, SEM images of all irradiated samples (Fig. S5) revealed no noticeable morphological changes compared to the untreated CLPs. Both the

agglomerate size and the primary particle size and shape remained practically unaffected, suggesting that the modifications occurred within the particles rather than through interparticle interactions.

Size Exclusion Chromatography (SEC) analysis suggested that lignin molecules from CLPs undergo repolymerization upon UV irradiation. This is evidenced by an increase in average molecular weight (Mw) for AL, OS, and SKL CLPs over the irradiation period. A similar trend can be observed for EH and EH2 CLPs until day 10 of irradiation, thereafter a slight decrease in Mw is ascertained (Table 2). While most studies indicate that UV irradiation of lignin primarily induces depolymerization and photo-oxidation, this conclusion is largely based on solubilized lignin systems [47,48] or lignin embedded within wood matrices [24]. However, studies on solid lignin have reported distinct behavior, with cross-linking and stabilization reactions occurring instead [49]. Further, the increase in polydispersity values over the irradiation period suggests that the samples become increasingly more polydisperse as a result of UV irradiation.

Among the samples investigated, EH2 and AL CLPs exhibited the highest relative changes in molecular weight during irradiation, followed by EH CLPs. In contrast, OS and SKL CLPs displayed only minor molecular weight variations, indicating a lower degree of polymerization or structural rearrangement under UV exposure Fig. 4. Radical formation due to the UV absorption can lead to radical–radical coupling between phenoxy radicals and carbon-centered radicals from $\beta\text{-O-4}$ cleavage. These findings indicated that both depolymerization and polymerization occur simultaneously during the irradiation process. This observation provides initial evidence that lignin, in the form of CLPs, exhibits self-stabilization mechanisms under UV irradiation at the studied concentration of 1.8 mg/mL .

For the UV/Vis spectroscopy, samples were dissolved in aqueous ethanol solutions, and the obtained spectra were area normalized (Eq. (1)) to investigate the irradiated samples qualitatively. The absorption spectra revealed minor differential behavior of CLPs derived from

Fig. 3. Intensity-weighted particle size distribution of irradiated of AL (a), OS (b), EH (c), EH2 (d) and SKL (e) during UV Irradiation experiments with UV-Pen Set-Up (1 to 14 d) measured by MADLS (1–14).

Table 2
Molecular weight (weight based) values and dispersity values (PDI) of long-term irradiated CLP suspensions.

Time (day)	AL		OS		EH		EH2		SKL	
	Mw (Da)	\mathcal{D}_M								
0	1795	1.55	1799	1.55	1710	1.54	1559	1.70	1604	1.60
1	1992	1.80	1845	1.70	1998	1.81	1607	1.79	1679	1.68
3	2223	1.91	1905	1.73	2229	1.90	2195	2.09	1719	1.71
7	2728	2.09	1999	1.78	2598	2.05	2198	2.06	1804	1.76
10	2857	2.13			2767	2.14	2314	2.08	2021	1.92
11	2889	2.13	2087	1.80			2387	2.13	1990	1.84
14	2942	2.14	2231	1.86	2611	2.06	2073	1.95	2058	1.91

Fig. 4. Minimum and maximum values of molecular weight (Mw) of irradiated CLPs including differences Δ in %.

different raw materials after UV irradiation. As shown in Fig. 5, AL CLPs exhibited an increase in absorption around 260 nm, accompanied by a slight decrease in the 320–350 nm region. In contrast, OS CLPs showed minimal spectral changes, slightly increasing around 300–320 nm and decreasing between 340 and 370 nm. For EH and EH2 CLPs, similar spectral changes to AL CLPs were observed in the 250–290 nm range, characterized by a moderate increase in absorption. Further, a progressive increase in absorption between 300 and 330 nm was evidenced over the irradiation period. Among all samples, SKL CLPs exhibited the most pronounced structural modifications, marked by a significant increase in absorption between 250 and 290 nm and a substantial decrease in the 320–360 nm range.

The increase in UV absorption within the 250–280 nm range after UV irradiation of SKL, AL, and both EH CLP types was likely associated with structural modifications and oxidation-induced chromophore formation. UV exposure in an aqueous medium promotes the oxidation of phenolic hydroxyl groups, forming quinones and conjugated carbonyl structures, which absorb strongly in this range [48,50]. In addition to photodegradation, UV exposure can facilitate crosslinking reactions, influencing the overall UV absorption properties, particularly in high-condensed lignins like softwood kraft lignin [51]. The observed blue shift in the UV absorption peak from 320 to 340 nm to 300–320 nm in AL and OS CLPs and the increased absorption in EH and EH2 CLP samples at 300–320 nm after UV irradiation suggested the breakdown of extended conjugated structures, particularly those involving quinones, stilbenes, and other long-chain chromophores. These spectral changes indicate oxidation processes, structural rearrangements, fragmentation and depolymerization reactions [48,52,53]. Furthermore, the substantial decrease in the UV absorption peak at 300–360 nm observed in SKL CLP samples after UV irradiation could primarily be attributed to the photodegradation of lignin chromophores, particularly the breakdown of conjugated phenolic and formation of quinone structures [54].

Based on the UV absorbance and molecular weight properties, it was evident that the exposure of CLPs to an external perturbation like UV irradiation induced molecular-level changes, which resulted in spectral variations in the infrared region such as intensity changes, band shifts, or changes in the band shapes. The chemical information provided by the FTIR spectra was therefore processed and evaluated by chemometrics using a principal component analysis (PCA). PCA exploratory analysis reduces the original spectroscopic data into an alternative presentation of variables such as scores and loadings, helping to examine chemical differences between irradiated colloidal lignin samples and identify the variables that contribute most to this differentiation.

The PCA model described the spectral variance in the range of 1900–750 cm^{-1} with four principal components (PCs) explaining 98.83 % of the cumulative variance. Plotting the PC scores against each other

can reveal clustering patterns within the dataset, grouping samples with similar chemical compositions. The scores plot for the PC1 versus PC2 is shown in Fig. 6a. PC1 with 67.73 % of the spectral variance and clearly discriminates lignin samples according to the extraction processes and source. Both SKL and AL showed a negative score in PC1 while OS, EH and EH2 were located on the positive side. Apparently, PC1 was influenced by the monomeric composition of lignins; lignins with higher syringyl content showed positive scores in PC1, while lignins with higher guaiacyl content presented negative scores. The loading plots evidenced the importance of original variables (bands) that mostly contribute to the separation of lignin samples in each PC. The loadings of PC1 (Fig. 6b) showed a high influence of the bands at 1330 and 1120 cm^{-1} , which are characteristic for syringyl (S) ring breathing and aromatic C–H in plane deformation of syringyl unit, respectively.

Additionally, PC2, with 25.61 % of the variance, described the evolution of lignin samples over time under UV exposure. As irradiation time increases, all lignin samples tend to shift in the same direction in PC2, indicating progressive chemical changes (Fig. 6c). EH and AL CLPs, in particular, show a significant shift after 7 days of irradiation, suggesting that they undergo more pronounced chemical changes compared to other CLPs. The key spectral bands contributing to PC2 include an intense peak with a shoulder in the range of 1800–1600 cm^{-1} , which correspond to C=O stretch of conjugated and unconjugated carbonyl groups, a band at 1170 cm^{-1} related to C–O stretching vibration of phenolic units, and the presence of –HC=CH– out-of-plane deformation. The largest difference in CLPs over irradiation time resulted from the formation of oxygen-containing functional groups as ketones (in quinones) arise due to oxidation processes evidencing modifications in hydroxyl and ether groups due to UV exposure. PC3, containing 3.56 % of the spectral information, clearly discriminated OS from EH types. According to the PC3 loading plot (data not shown), this separation may be attributed to differences in the structural functionalities characteristic of each lignin type.

The results suggest that the reactions ongoing in colloidal lignin particles under UV irradiation are a dual process involving oxidative degradation and radical-induced crosslinking. The UV absorbance and FTIR spectra confirmed the formation of oxidized functionalities, while molecular weight data reflected the simultaneous degradation (an increase of polydispersity) and crosslinking (Mw increase). This observation provides initial evidence supporting our hypothesis that lignin, in the form of CLPs, exhibits self-stabilization mechanisms under irradiation.

3.3. The effect of the CLPs concentration and matrix

To evaluate the effect of CLP concentration on photostability and validate the hypothesis that CLPs undergo self-stabilizing and crosslinking reactions during UV irradiation, experiments were conducted using suspensions of EH2-derived CLPs at three concentrations: EH2 (1.8 mg/mL), EH2 D1 (0.72 mg/mL), and EH2 D2 (0.36 mg/mL). The irradiated samples were analyzed by UV–Vis spectroscopy, HPSEC and MADLS. The results indicated that for the EH2 D1 sample, only minor changes in the absorbance spectra occur until day 3, as shown by the similarity in absorbance values to those of the original undiluted EH2 samples (Fig. 7). In contrast, the EH2 D2 sample exhibited a marked decrease in absorbance at ~ 285 nm by day 3, suggesting that lower concentrations are more susceptible to UV-induced degradation. The integrated absorbance values over time (240–400 nm), plotted in Fig. 7d, demonstrated that the sample with the highest particle concentration (EH2) exhibited minimal changes in absorption capacity over time, indicating greater structural stability. In contrast, more diluted samples (D1 and D2) showed a pronounced decrease in absorption capacity over time, with the lowest concentration sample losing nearly all absorption capacity after 10 days.

The average molecular weight (Mw) of the irradiated samples was monitored over a 14-day period. During the first three days, all CLP

Fig. 5. Area normalized absorption spectra of AL (a), OS (b), EH (c), EH2 (d) and SKL (e) during UV Irradiation experiments with UV-Pen Set-Up (1 to 14 d; 0.1 mg/mL CLP; 60 wt% aqueous EtOH).

concentrations exhibited a similar increase in Mw, indicating an initial phase of molecular restructuring. However, beyond this period, distinct differences emerged. For the highest concentration sample (EH2), Mw showed a gradual increase from day 3 to day 13, followed by a decline, suggesting a balance between cross-linking and degradation processes. In contrast, the intermediate concentration sample (EH2 D1) continued cross-linking until day 7 before undergoing depolymerization. The lowest concentration sample (EH2 D2) exhibited the earliest onset of

depolymerization, beginning after just three days of irradiation, ultimately reaching the lowest Mw values among all tested samples (Fig. 8). Maximum and minimum values reached during the irradiation time are plotted in Fig. 8b, as well as the percental difference of those values. Hence, the highest value for molecular weight change of the irradiated samples can be observed for the lowest concentration of CLPs EH2 D2. Optical analysis of the irradiated samples revealed a clear temporal variation in color fading for the D1 (a) and D2 (b) dilutions, as presented

Fig. 6. PCA analysis: a) scores PCA 1 and 2, b) loadings of PC1 and c) loadings of PC2.

in Fig. S6. An important observation is the slight darkening of the irradiated samples after one day of exposure. This color change suggests the formation of new chromophoric groups as a possible explanation for the observed darkening. After 14 days of UV irradiation, the D1 diluted suspension retained a faint yellow hue, while the D2 dilution appeared completely colorless under the same conditions. The irradiated samples of EH2 did not reveal optical changes. Particle size analysis using MADLS on day 14 at higher dilutions did not detect the presence of particles, suggesting their disintegration over the irradiation period and

indicating a loss of colloidal integrity under prolonged UV exposure.

To further assess the factors influencing UV-induced degradation, we investigated the role of the matrix during UV irradiation. The rationale for this study was based on the formation of radicals during the UV irradiation within water, which can facilitate the degradation of cross-linked polymers.

Firstly, the CLP suspensions were air-dried and subsequently exposed to UV irradiation using the UV chamber set-up to investigate their behavior under UV radiation in a non-aqueous environment (solid

Fig. 7. Absorption spectra of EH2 CLPs irradiated at different concentrations a) EH2 (1.8 mg/mL), b) EH2 D1 (0.72 mg/mL), c) EH2 D2 (0.36 mg/mL) and d) Integrated UV absorption values of EH 2 CLP suspensions at different concentrations over irradiation time (1 to 14 d; measured at 0.1 mg/mL CLP; 60 wt% aqueous EtOH).

Fig. 8. a) Molecular weight (weight based) of EH 2 CLP suspensions at different concentrations over 14 days irradiation time, and b) Minimum and maximum values of molecular weight (Mw) of irradiated EH 2 CLPs at different concentrations including differences Δ in %.

state). It is important to note that, despite air-drying process, residual moisture may still be present in the samples. Samples were collected after 72, 164, 332, 501 and 669 h (corresponding 3, 7, 14, 21 and 25 days) of irradiation and analyzed. The UV absorbance results indicated that no significant structural changes occur until day 21 of UV irradiation. A slight decrease around 280 nm and a very small increase from 380 to 400 nm after 25 days of UV irradiation suggest, that de- and

repolymerization reaction might be initiated at this point (Fig. 9a).

Additionally, hexane was selected as a non-reactive and UV-stable matrix for irradiation experiments. Therefore, CLPs were freeze-dried and re-dispersed in hexane before irradiation. The findings indicate that the matrix plays a significant role in both crosslinking and degradation processes under UV exposure. According to UV-Vis spectra (Fig. 9b), no absorbance changes in the CLP chemistry were noticed.

Fig. 9. Absorption spectra of a) air-dried EH2 CLPs; UV-Chamber Set-Up; 72–669 h and b) EH 2 CLP in hexane; UV-Pen set-up; (measured at 0.1 mg/mL CLP; 60 wt% aqueous EtOH).

Fig. 10 illustrates the distinct molecular weight evolution of EH2-derived CLPs under UV irradiation in three different environments: aqueous suspension, solid-state, and hexane. In aqueous conditions (EH2), the CLPs exhibit a pronounced increase in molecular weight within the first three days, followed by moderate fluctuations, suggesting a dynamic balance between cross-linking and degradation reactions. In contrast, CLPs irradiated in solid-state, and hexane show more gradual and consistent increases in molecular weight, indicative of dominant cross-linking or self-stabilization mechanisms, with minimal degradation.

The largest molecular weight shift, up to 53 %, was observed in the aqueous suspension (Fig. 10b), reflecting the higher reactivity of CLPs in water. This behavior may result from the dual role of lignin: stabilizing the radicals and reinforcing its own structure under these conditions. These findings are consistent with the work of Duran et al. [49], who reported different UV-induced behaviors between solubilized and solid lignin. Importantly, the transformation of lignin into colloidal particles appears to enhance its stability, particularly under UV stress, supporting its potential as a robust, bio-based material for applications requiring prolonged light exposure.

4. Conclusion

In this study, five technical lignins were successfully transformed into colloidal lignin particles (CLPs) using a solvent-shifting method,

with the aim of investigating their photochemical behavior under UV irradiation. The custom UV-pen setup demonstrated clear advantages over conventional UV irradiation chambers, offering improved control and effectiveness for UV exposure experiments, particularly in aqueous media. Despite the inherent heterogeneity of the raw lignin feedstocks, the resulting CLPs exhibited comparable responses to UV irradiation in water, suggesting that the combination of solvent-induced fractionation and nanoparticle formation yields particles with similar physicochemical properties. The photochemical behavior of the CLPs was strongly influenced by both their concentration in suspension and the nature of the surrounding medium. Notably, chemical modifications occurred primarily within individual particles, rather than through interparticle interactions. In aqueous media at high concentrations, CLPs exhibited a dual self-stabilization mechanism under UV irradiation, characterized by the simultaneous formation of oxidized functional groups and radical-induced crosslinking, likely initiated by phenoxy radicals. At lower concentrations, a similar radical formation and coupling occurred initially, but it was followed by rapid photodegradation and depolymerization, as evidenced by the appearance of low-molecular-weight fragments, reduced UV absorption capacity, and the loss of colloids (disappearance of particles). In non-aqueous (hexane) or solid-state conditions, the extent of UV-induced changes were minimal due to limited molecular mobility and reduced radical generation. Overall, these findings provide valuable insights into the stability and degradation pathways of CLPs under different environmental conditions. The

Fig. 10. Molecular weight (weight based) of EH 2 CLP suspensions in different matrices over irradiation time (1 to 14d) and b) Minimum and maximum values of molecular weight (Mw) of irradiated EH 2 CLPs in different matrices including differences Δ in %.

results indicate that the particles exhibit prolonged stability under UV irradiation, highlighting their potential as durable natural UV filters. This aligns with a safe-by-design approach, offering a sustainable and bio-based alternative for photoprotective formulations. The study also underscores the relevance of CLP behavior in aquatic ecosystems, contributing to the understanding of their long-term environmental impact and the potential for controlled degradation in natural environments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Julia Tomasich: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **René Herrera Díaz:** Data curation. **Anna Sandak:** Writing – review & editing. **Michael Harasek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Stefan Beisl:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Conceptualization. **Oihana Gordobil:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Julia Tomasich reports financial support and equipment, drugs, or supplies were provided by Lignovations GmbH. Julia Tomasich reports a relationship with Lignovations GmbH that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.147204>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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